

Work-Life and Employees' Performance of Female Staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo State.

Okpiabhele Emmanuella (PhD)

Corresponding Author

Achievers University Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria

osarenmen@gmail.com

Adesida Adejoke Rachael

Achievers University Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria

Adesidaadejoke11@gmail.com

Yomi-Daramola Olukemi Mercy

Rufus Giwa Polytechnic Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria

Mercyomidams02@gmail.com

Ebiniyi Olufunmilayo Olajire

Rufus Giwa Polytechnic Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria

febiniyi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study evaluates the relationship between work-life balance and employee performance of female staff at Achievers University Owo, Ondo state. Long-Working Hours (LWH), Leisure or Relaxation Time (LRT) and Stress Level (SL) were used to examine the relationship between work-life balance and employees' performance (EP). Using the sample size of 105 questionnaires were administered to female staff of the institution only while 98 were retrieved for analysis. A correlational research design was adopted for the study while Descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple regression alongside ANOVA were carried out for data analysis using SPSS (26). The results revealed that LWH shows a positive and significant relationship with EP; LRT reveals a negative and significant relationship with EP while SL was positive and insignificantly related to EP. In conclusion, it was discovered that work-life balance is significantly related to employees' performance if the institution provides better organizational practices that will reduce stress and health challenges for female staff in other to enhance their performance. It was therefore recommended that the institution should provide a quality working schedule that the female staff would benefit from to reduce stress and workload. Also, they should provide vacation periods for female staff in the institution and finally, female staff should create a strategy in reducing stress at the workplace for better performance.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Long-Working Hours, Leisure or Relaxation Time, Stress Level and Employees' Performance

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Employees in Nigeria are faced with issues ranking between non-official activities and official activities which results in a work-life imbalance that increases the stress level of employees, less productivity, increased absenteeism and turnover, and drug abuse amongst others which affects the performance of employees (Mmakwe & Ojiabo, 2018; Kadnan, 2019). Most organizations have come to realize the reason for work-life balance as regards the performance of employees and they now offer flexible working hours, leisure and relaxation time, and daycare centres in order to motivate employees (VeenaLatha, 2019; Akpa *et al.*, 2019). Presently, working women are no longer regarded as taboo but were limited to domestic activities in the past but this limitation no longer stands as they could be seen working in many places such as public and private sectors even as leaders (Sharma *et al.*, 2019). From Nigeria's perspective, the burden of roles and responsibilities on employees is often caused by changes in demographic, dual career couples, the rate of single parents and employee's reluctance in accepting long-working hours (Ogechi & Nwaeke, 2019; Ledum *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, the rate of women's participation has increased especially in tertiary institutions where female students have increased also and they occupy job vacancies in the labour market which leads to a great struggle for female employees in balancing the role between home and workplace where the deal in fulfilling their employer's expectations as well as taking responsibilities of their family during and after working hours (Hussin *et al.*, 2019; Melayansari & Bhinekawati, 2020).

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

In some business environments, female employees are being faced with work-life balance issues and it is believed that the role of women in society has guaranteed progress, long-term development and stability as well as the primary caretaker of both the elderly and children in every society (Basak, 2021). In an environment where there is a high level of competitive pressure the penalties of this on employees are enormous and it has become an increasingly prevalent of great concern to various employees in both private and public sectors as regards work-life balance in the area of pressures that work has on the life of the employees as well as a family which triggered research bordering on work-life balance (Adegboyega & Babatunde, 2022; Biswal & Mishra, 2022; Khan *et al.*, 2023).

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Ledum *et al* (2020) highlighted major issues that may hinder employee performance when work-life balance incentives such as relaxation time, leave entitlement, welfare policies as well as family are not observed by the management of these firms, may lead some employees to work around the clock with little attention to themselves and their families, which may lead to issues. Work-life balance has started giving homes and organizations concern as regards the importance and effects on various sectors and employees (Sharma *et al.*, 2019; Okeke *et al.*, 2022). The idea that personal life and paid work are competing priorities rather than complementary elements has called for research because a healthy work-life balance creates great significance for working females, particularly in the present current context in which both, the family and the workplace have posed several challenges and problems for females (Gambo *et al.*, 2022).

The edge between work and family, consequences has been identified to play a significant role in female employees in tertiary institutions. Previous researchers have focused attention on female

employees of other work sectors such as information technology, Sharma *et al.*, (2019); Fernando & Kavitha, (2020); Balamurugan & Sreeleka, (2020); Manoharan *et al.*, (2022), banking sector Anukwuocha & Okafor, (2020); Siwale, (2020); Mwiikisa, (2020); Aynalem, (2020); Okeke *et al.*, (2022); Khan *et al.*, (2023), public sectors Hassan *et al.*, (2017); Melayansari & Bhinekawati, (2020); Basak (2021), hospitals Pulhin, (2020) with little attention to tertiary institutions and studies carried out were majorly on female teachers in public schools, female academic staff in public universities Hussin *et al.*, (2019); Shukria, (2021); Noronha & Aithal, (2020); Oak, (2023) but in Nigeria studies carried out were few such as Asiyanbi & Kazeem (2019); Nwagbara (2020); Gambo *et al.* (2022) It is evident that the empirical studies which focused on the link between work-life balance and female employee performance have divergent views thus, complementing the existing empirical studies by carrying out the study in private tertiary institutions in Owo, Ondo state.

Also, most studies made use of flexible scheduling, employee assistance program, annual maternity and sick leave, job sharing, social life, family leave programs, institutional pressure, socio-cultural pressure, and leave policy amongst others in measuring the work-life balance of female employees but long-working hours, leisure or relaxation time as well as stress level have not been used in measuring the work-life balance of female employees in Nigeria. Another area is the methodology most of these studies carried out their analysis using partial least square, structural equation modelling, and multiple regression. The reviewed study shows mixed results and this may be attributed to the estimation methodologies and span of data used as well as the location of the study. This study, therefore, presents useful knowledge on work-life balance and employee performance of female staff in Achievers University, Owo, Ondo state.

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

1.2 Research Questions

For this study, the under-listed research questions have been highlighted below:

- i. How do long-working hours influence employees' performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo state?
- ii. To what extent has leisure or relaxation time impacted employees' performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo state?
- iii. What is the relationship between stress level and employees' performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo state?

1.3 Research Objectives

This study seeks to:

- i. Examine the influence of long-working hours on employee performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo state.
- ii. evaluate to what extent leisure or relaxation time impacts employees' performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo state.
- iii. to find out the relationship between stress level and employee performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo state.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The study evaluates the relationship between work-life balance and employees' performance using long-working hours, leisure and relaxation time, and stress level as components in measuring work-life balance which serves as the independent variable against employees' performance (dependent variable). A correlational research design was adopted using a primary source of data with a sample size of 105 (one hundred and five) which was done using cluster random probability sampling technique of both academic and non-academic female staff of Achievers University. Multiple regression analysis was carried out alongside ANOVA using SPSS version 26. The timeframe for this study was within the month of September, 2023 to January, 2024.

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360)

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Employees' Performance

Employees' performance is the work achievement of an individual after putting the required effort into accomplishing the work responsibilities (Pradhan & Jena, 2017). Though several factors are tied to the success of the organization in all these aspects, employees are the most important factor and the main reason why organizational objectives could be accomplished. Low employees' performance or productivity can lead the organization to fail in its organizational goals (Ameen & Baharom, 2019). Moreover, some factors impact employees' performance such as skill level, turnover, adaptability, intrinsic motivation, productivity, skill flexibility, commitment and absenteeism (Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2019). According to Odeloye *et al* (2020), an employee's outstanding performance is vital to the workplace because organizational success depends on an employee's innovation, dedication and creativity and it helps the firm to increase and utilize the capacity of human resources thus, achieve this organization need to make policies that will encourage employee performance since employee's job performance depends on or is a consequence of some grouping of opportunity, effort and ability, effort, and opportunity (Ledum *et al.*, 2020; Okeke *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, employee performance is a central point in any organization because the ultimate performance of organizations depends on the policies geared towards increasing the performance of employees (Gambo *et al.*, 2022).

2.2 Work-life Balance

VeenaLatha (2019) opined that work-life balance is the interaction between work and other activities that include family, leisure, social obligations, personal development, health and community thereby striking a balance and it does not signify an equal balance in units of time

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

between work and life, but about the proper understanding of the priorities of the personal level and professional which has to do with prioritizing between lifestyle and work (Sharma *et al.*, 2019). Ola *et al* (2019) described work-life balance as a blend of interactions among different realms of one's life, such as work-life, religion amongst others and can be summed up as a consistent process of finding time for loved ones, interests, friends, self-care, personal development, involvement in community activities in to work in the workplace priorities. Nandipati (2021) suggested that work-life balance is all about fine-tuning work patterns to achieve overall fulfilment and a good work-life balance enables the business to thrive and at the same time enables the employees to easily combine work with other aspirations and responsibilities (Mamta, 2021).

According to Gambo *et al* (2022), work-life balance is having a degree of control over where, when and how an individual work, leading to being able to enjoy an optimal quality of life and this is achieved when an individual is fulfilled both in life and outside its paid work is accepted as well as respected in the mutual benefit of the individual, organization as well as the society. Recently, employees struggle to strike a balance between their personal lives and career and when these two are out of place most times leads to decreases performance and increases mental tension (Biswal & Mishra, 2022). Though work-life is an important phenomenon which is of great concern to employees both in public and private sectors, it focused on the capability to link between private life and the career of an individual and past studies have confirmed that work-life balance among females plays an important role in living a successful career life and personal life (Okeke *et al.*, 2022; Khan *et al.*, 2023).

2.2.1 Long-working hours

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

Female in different fields and positions have different level of balance as well as career mothers who experience certain issues because of childbearing amongst others suffers work-life imbalance due to the nature of their job and organizations not supporting them either by providing good working conditions, job scheduling and family not being supportive (Mazerolle & Barrett, 2018). Some employees experience long-working hours which causes fatigue, irritability, mood swings and low performance. hence, maintaining a work-life balance assists in decreasing these issues and prevents fatigue and others (Odeloye *et al.*, 2020). Due to the physiological and psychological symptoms employees may experience which include anxiety, anger, moodiness and dissatisfaction, conquering such issues organizations need to put into consideration balancing the work-life of employees (Tamunomiebi & Oyibo, 2020). Thus, long-working hours can be managed as a substitute work or job schedule where the transaction of responsibilities is designated between the number of days or weekly hours. But need to strictly adhere to create a positive impact on recruitment, morale, turnover and productivity (Tsedenia, 2020).

2.2.2 Leisure or relaxation time

The standard flexible work programs include job sharing, flexible shifting work, relaxation time, and part-time work amongst others and employees must indicate their demands and desires from their firm since employee's inability to fulfil their responsibility is because of work-life imbalance (Mwangi *et al.*, 2018; Muthulakshmi, 2018; Sutha, 2019). Leisure or relaxation time has been seen as one of the key elements of organisational support which enables employees to balance their work-life (Shaikh *et al.*, 2019). These are arrangements done between the employer and employee in agreement to the scheduling of time that will make them access to leisure, childcare, and parental leave amongst others (Tamunomiebi & Oyibo, 2020). While doing so it enables employees to

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

choose when and how to finish their responsibilities within a specific time (Odeloye *et al.*, 2020). This can assist in addressing issues or challenges employees encounter at the workplace and in return protect the health and well-being of the employees which in return increases their performance (Agari, 2022). Thus, maintaining a balance work-life is important because of its impact on increasing employee performance as well as organizational productivity. And with leisure or relaxation time schedules becomes a key element as it enables one to balance professional and personal lives equally. (Biswal & Mishra, 2022).

2.2.3 Stress Level

Female workers in different positions and fields do have various levels of balance which create an imbalance in work-life for them because of more levels of stress which may involve excess workload, working environment, and nature of the job amongst others (Mazerolle & Barrett, 2018). Some workload involves a deadline for each document or project submission which may arises the stress level of employees that are being pressured by top management, and direct bosses at the workplace (Balamurugan & Sreeleka, 2020). According to Fernando and Kavitha (2020) with today's competitive period, changes in demands, regulations much pressure in the workplace needs have improved a lot and which leads to an increase in the stress level of female employees.

Basak (2021) defined job stress as an individual's insight about the work environment as demanding, threatening or discomfort experienced individuals in the workplace and work-life balance has been linked to the varied levels of job stress among employees in various occupations. Though physical conditions may differ from individual and fatigue can impact the personal situation in terms of unpleasant feelings as well as sickness directly which has close correlations

to personal life satisfaction (Taghinejad, 2021). Moreso, the demands usually connected to the job

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360)

and outside of working life have been observed as the key to influencing psychological health by declining stressful situations and conflict (Wang, 2021). Also, stress influences the performance of professionals not only at the workplace but also on the domestic front and it is required for professionals to perform effectively on both fronts. And woman or female employees experienced anxiety during time spent achieving a work-life balance which results to pressure and poor execution. Most outcomes uncovered that numerous female employees have ignored their well-being during the time spent enhancing the lives of their relatives and their understudies (Oak, 2023).

2.3 Relationship between work-life Balance and Organizational Performance

In determining the relationship that between work-life balance and employees' performance as regards female staff in the workplace some of the previous studies revealed that there is a significant relationship between work-life balance and female employees' performance as well as the challenges women faced within the workplace and personal home activities (Mendis & Weerakkody, 2017; Asiyani & Kazeem, 2019; Anukwuocha & Okafor, 2020; Aynalem, 2020; Adhitama & Riyanto, 2020). Gambo *et al* (2020) studies revealed a significant effect of WLB on the performance of female staff (Fernando & Kavitha, 2020). Though some factors affect WLB as they serve as a beneficial impact on women's lives and most times prolonged working hours while marital status, and increase income do have beneficial effects on the performance of women (Khan *et al.*, 2023). Nwagbara (2020) stated that there are some challenges in terms of policies and practices at the workplace which are detrimental to employees' performance, but these policies do affect when negatively practiced (Okeke *et al.*, 2022).

2.4 Conceptual Framework

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

Figure 2.0: Conceptual paradigm
(Researcher's conceptualization, 2024)

From the above diagram, work-life balance (independent variable) is measured with long-working hours, leisure or relaxation time and stress levels while employees' performance is the dependent variable.

2.5 Theoretical Review

2.5.1 Spill-Over Theory

This theory suggests that there is a similarity between what occurs at the workplace and in the home and it emphasizes the tendency of the employee to manage their emotions, skills, behaviours and attitudes that they create at work into their family life also vice versa (Sidin *et al.*, 2010). Dex and Bond (2005) opined that though the edge between work and home is relatively weak and tends to spill over positive or negative spills into the home or workplace (Lewis, 1997; Morris & Maden, 2007; Grzywacz & Marks, 2000). From an organizational perspective, positive spillover theory can have a direct impact on organizational financial well-being where a satisfied employee will

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

have a spillover effect on their customer as well, thereby increasing organizational performance (Carlson *et al.*, 2006; Greenhaus & Powell, 2006). While the presence of negative spillover between work and family is most frequently characterized by various types of work and family conflict or interference. But reoccurring negative events such as stressors, on the same day in multiple domains or from one individual to another are also regarded as part of negative spillover (Carlson *et al.*, 2006; Mulanya & Kagiri, 2018).

2.5.2 Work or Family Border Theory

According to Clark (2000) which aims at giving details of how an individual manages and negotiates the family and work domains as well as the borders between them to gain balance. According to this theory, flexibility and absorptivity of borders between employees' family and work lives will affect the ease of transitions, the level of integration and the level of conflict between these domains. (Bellavia & Frone, 2005). Family and work are seen as separate domains or worlds which are associated with different thoughts, rules, behaviour and patterns while borders are delineating between domains indicating the points at which domain-specific behaviour can start and finish (Guest, 2002). Moreso, there are three major types of borders which are physical, temporal and psychological borders which makes family or work border theory different from that of boundary theory (Desrochers & Sargent, 2003).

Thus, this theory focuses on managing boundaries or borders between scopes of life and it emphasizes that there should be a suitable balance between work and family life involvements and it is relevant to this study because it is a useful way of knowing work-life balance which has been critiqued and it is largely gender-blind (Emsline & Hunt, 2009). Regarding the outcome of employees' daily lives based on the concept of the border theory, some researchers have expressed

concern about women's double burden due to the blurring of the boundary between family and work (Jacobs & Gerson, 2000). It deals with family and work domains and other aspects of life such as leave benefits, wellness, and flexible relaxation and it also mainly deals with caregivers, sports for wellness, needs of parents, socializing and leisure amongst others. Thus, this theory stands as a base for this study.

2.6 Empirical Review

Asiyanbi and Kazeem (2019) examined the influence of work-life balance on job performance among the teachers in the Ibadan North local government area of Oyo state. Sharma *et al* (2019) worked on a survey using a self-designed questionnaire among 188 employees working in various service sectors of Madhya Pradesh using principal component factor analysis with varimax rotation. Hussin *et al* (2019) aimed at the implications of the work-life balance of female workers on their quality of life. Melayansari and Bhinekawati (2020) investigated the impact of work-life balance on employee performance mediated by employee loyalty in the context of female employees working in an international environment in greater Jakarta, Indonesia. Anukwuocha and Okafor (2020) examined the effect of work-life balance on employee performance. It shows that there is a significant effect of work-life balance on employee performance of First Bank PLC. Nwagbara (2020) examined the relationship between the institution's organizational work-life balance (WLB) policies and practices and subsequent challenges faced by Nigerian female workers. Fernando and Kavitha (2020) evaluated work-life balance and how it causes stress among female employees working in the IT sector. Pulhin (2020) assessed work-life balance of women employees particularly in the fast-food industry using a descriptive-survey method with 175 women employees of fast-food establishments in Batangas Province. Noronha and Aithal (2020)

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

studied the level of challenges faced by women teachers in maintaining work-life balance with special reference to state universities of Karnataka. Balamurugan and Sreeleka (2020) from their findings described how women employees are balanced and satisfied in the IT sector and the factors that affect the work-life balance of women employees are working hours, Job satisfaction, and working condition amongst others. Aynalem (2020) examined the effect of work-life balance on women's work performance in the commercial bank of Ethiopia. Mwiikisa, (2020) examined the management of work-life balance and employee performance in the banking sector. Basak (2021) identifies the factors that affect maintaining the proper work-life balance of working women in Bangladesh during the COVID-19 pandemic. Shukria (2021) evaluated the factors impacting the work-life balance of female employees in private higher education institutions in Kabul, Afghanistan. Gambo *et al.* (2022) examined the effect of work-life balance on employee performance of the female academic staff of the University of Jos. Okeke *et al.* (2022) examined the effect of work-life balance and female employee performance in selected deposit money banks in Anambra state and investigated the relationship between leave policy, flexible scheduling, employee assistance and work environment on female employee performance. Khan *et al.* (2023) investigated how work-life balance affects the personal lives of women working in the banking industry of Larkana City, Pakistan result revealed that a good WLB had a beneficial impact on working women's personal lives where prolonged working hours had a detrimental impact on women's personal lives, while, income packages and marital status had beneficial effects.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlational research design. Correlational research design is a means of establishing the relationship between two closely connected variables Bostley, (2019). The reason

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360)

for this design is to identify variables that have a direct relationship that causes the change in one to create a certain change in the other and this type of research is descriptive in nature. This was appropriate for the study since it sought to examine the relationship between work-life balance and employee performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo state. The population of this study consists of academic and non-academic female staff of Achievers University Owo, Ondo State with a total of 142 (one hundred and forty-two). The study sampling size is 105 (one hundred and five) female staff of Achievers University Owo, Ondo state. The sampling technique used for this study was stratified random probability sampling technique using the Taro Yamane formula in determining the sample size for this study.

Primary data were sourced through the use of a questionnaire and the statement items were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD). Hence, the questionnaire was used to seek information about respondents' demographic data and perception of work-life balance and employee performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo State. Face and content validity were used for the research instrument as well as the result of the reliability test shows that each of the variables is reliable since the total overall test was 0.826 coefficient which is illustrated below.

Table 3.1: Result of Reliability Test (n⁼)

Construct	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
LWH	4	0.913
LRT	4	0.767
SL	4	0.823
Overall Alpha		0.826

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024.

3.1 Method of Data Analysis

Data analysis consists of descriptive statistics, and multiple regression analysis as well as analysis of variances (ANOVA), model summaries and regression coefficients were used to describe the characteristics of the study population. Excel and Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 were used as the principal data analysis tools and were presented in tables.

3.2 Model of Specification

This comprises the elements used in measuring the independent variable (Work-life balance) which consists of Long-Working Hours (LWH), Leisure or Relaxation Time (LRT) and Stress Level (SL) against the dependent variable Employee Performance (EP).

The model for the study is functionally stated below:

$$EP = f(LWH, LRT, SL) \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

The model is econometrically stated as:

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1LWH_i + \beta_2LRT_i + \beta_3SL_i + \epsilon_i \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Where:

FP = Employees' Performance

LWH = Long-Working Hours

LRT = Leisure or Relaxation Time

SL = Stress Level

β_0 = Intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_3 > 0$ = Coefficient of LWH, LRT and SL

ϵ_i = Error term

i = Samples of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo State.

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360)

The apriori expectation for this study is stated:

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0$, the reason is that the variables used here are a process dimension

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

From the total number of 110 (one hundred and ten) questionnaire distributed to female staff of Achievers University Owo, Ondo state, 98 (ninety-eight) questionnaire was retrieved representing 93% for analysis.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Demographic Characteristics	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	21 - 30 years	8	8
	31 - 40 years	23	24
	41 - 50 years	43	44
	51 and above	24	24
	Total	98	100
Marital Status	Married	51	52
	Single	29	30
	Widow/Widower	8	8
	Divorced/Separated	10	10
	Total	98	100

Qualification	O' Level	9	9
	ND/NCE	12	12
	HND/B.Sc.	41	42
	MBA/M.Sc.	27	28
	PhD	9	9
	Total	98	100
Work Experience	0 - 2 years	19	19
	3 - 5 years	52	53
	6 - 10 years	27	28
	Total	98	100
Designation	Academic	15	15
	Non-Academic	83	85
	Total	98	100

Source: Researchers' computation (2024)

From Table 4.1, 98 female respondents staff of Achievers University Owo, Ondo state were captured for age, 8 female staff representing (8%) ranged between 21-30 years, 23, (24%) of female staff captured were between 31-40 years, 43, (44%) of female staff ranged between 41-50 years while 24, (24%) were within the range of 51 years and above. This implies that most of the female staff at Achievers University are averagely young and fit for responsibilities. Out of 98 female respondents captured for marital status, 51 female staff representing (52.2%) were married, 29, (30%) were single, 8, (8%) were stated as widows/widowers and 10, (10%) were

recorded as divorced/separated. This implies that the majority of the female staff working at Achievers University Owo, are married. 98 female respondents recorded for qualification, 9 female staff obtained Ordinary Certificate representing (9%), 12 of them obtained ND/NCE representing (12%), and 41, (42%) attained HND/B.Sc, 27, (28%) were having either MBA or MSc while 9, (9%) were PhD holders. This shows that the institution has more BSc or HND certificates holders For work experience, out of 98 female respondents recorded, 19, (19%) have spent between 0 - 2 years, 52 (53%) have spent 3 - 5 years, 27 respondents representing (28%) have spent 6 - 10 years working experience in the institution. This indicates that the institution has more dedicated and competent female staff who have been with them for a long. Finally, 15 female respondents representing (15%) were academic staff while 83, (85%) recorded were non-academic staff of the institution. This implies that the institution has more non-academic female staff than academic female staff.

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Min	Max	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Stat	Stat	Stat	Stat	Stat	Stat	Std. Error
EP	98	5.771	1.64	1.611	1.412	.603	.632
LWH	98	4.367	4.31	11.081	2.231	.862	.651
LRT	98	5.111	8.51	14.542	2.671	.468	.621
SL	98	7.328	11.26	21.514	2.560	.065	.664
Valid N (listwise)	98						

Source: Researchers' Computation (2024)

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360>

The summary of descriptive statistics from the above table indicates that during the study under review, the average employees performance (EP) is 5.77 with a standard deviation of 1.412, a minimum of 1.64 and a maximum of 1.611, this implies that employees' performance is been determined based on how well female staff managed their activities at home as well as the workplace without encountering issues that might lead to health challenges amongst others. Long-working hours (LWH) on average is 4.367, with a standard deviation of 2.231 and minimum of 4.31, maximum of 11.081 which shows that long-working hours of female staff observed at the workplace do affect their impact on performance. Leisure or relaxation time (LRT) on average is 5.111 with a standard deviation of 2.671, a minimum value of 8.51 and a maximum value of 14.542 this indicates that the majority of the female staff do have time for leisure or relaxation as a common factor that influences work-life balance on their performance. Stress level (SL) on average is 7.328 with a standard deviation of 2.560, a minimum value of 11.26 and a maximum value of 21.514 this implies that the high level of job stress on female staff and do affect their performance

4.2.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 4.3: Pearson Correlation Matrix of the Dependent Variable and Independent Variable

Variable	EP	LWH	LRT	SL
EP	1.000			
LWH	.761**	1.000		
LRT	.624**	.621**	1.000	
SL	.701**	.564**	.661**	1.000
**Correlation is significant at the 0.000 level (2-tailed). Sample size =98				

Source: (SPSS Output Own Survey Result, 2024)

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323360>

The table above shows the relationship that exists between work-life balance variables (long-working hours, leisure or relaxation time and stress level) as against employee performance of female staff in Achievers University Owo, Ondo state. It revealed that long-working hours (LWH) are positively and strongly related to employees' performance at 0.761 representing 76%. Leisure or relaxation time (LRT) shows a positive and average relationship with employees' performance at 0.624 representing 62% while stress level (SL) indicates a positive and strong relationship with employees' performance at 0.701 representing 70%. Therefore, the table presented shows that the variables tested were significant statistically at 0.000 which indicates that work-life balance has a direct relationship with employees' performance.

4.2.3 Regression Analysis

Table 4.4 Multiple Regression Results

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.671 ^a	.443	.316	1.84069		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Employees' Performance, Long-Working Hours, Leisure or Relaxation Time and Stress Level						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	264.650	61	67.462	18.132	.000 ^b
	Residual	1169.550	450	8.767		
	Total	1316.110	490			
a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Long-Working Hours, Leisure or Relaxation Time and Stress Level						
Coefficients						

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.310	1.152		2.005	.000
	Long-Working Hours	.256	.118	.242	2.169	.003
	Leisure or Relaxation Time	-.140	.064	-.165	-2.187	.000
	Stress Level	.186	.048	.226	3.875	.221
a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance						

Source: *Researcher's Computation (2024)*.

Source: SPSS Version 26.0

4.2.4 Discussion of Findings

The study evaluates the relationship between work-life balance and employee performance of female staff at Achievers University Owo, Ondo state. Three components of work-life balance were examined, long-working hours, leisure or relaxation time and stress level in relationship with the dependent variable employees' performance. From the findings long-working hours (LWH) shows a coeff-value of 0.256, t-value of 2.169 and P-value of 0.003 which is positive and significantly related to employees' performance. which implies that most female staff at Achievers University are during long-working hours but are being scheduled to avoid stress and underperformance. This is related to the studies of Balamurugan and Sreeleka (2020); Tsendenia (2020); Shukria (2021) but did not align with the study carried out by Khan *et al* (2023) which was negatively insignificant to employees' performance. Leisure or relaxation time (LRT) has a coeff-value of -0.140, t-value -2.187 and P-value 0.000 implying that it is negatively but significantly related to employees' performance which indicates that there is a standard flexible working

programme which involves relaxation time, leisure, job and shifting of work. Also, leisure or relaxation time is regarded as a key element of organizational support which enables female staff of Achievers University to balance their work-life. The result aligns with the studies of Kossek and Lautsch (2018); Sharma *et al* (2019); Shukria (2021); Basak (2021); Wang (2021); Verma and Gautam (2022); The results from Mwiikisa (2020); Okeke *et al* (2022) shows a positive and significant relationship but did not align with the study carried out by Ganbo *et al* (2022). Stress Level (SL) has a coeff-value of 0.186, t-value of 3.875 and P-value of 0.221 which means that SL is positively and insignificantly related to employees' performance. This implies that female staff of the university were not able to balance their stress level alongside work-life. Some female staff may not be able to meet up with deadlines or job schedules. Moreso, it means that they experience discomfort at the workplace as well as in personal situations. Some might not be satisfied with the job either it is demanding or they are affected psychologically by the stressful conditions they find themselves in. This study agrees with Hassan *et al* (2017); Basak (2021) But did not align with the studies carried out by Balamurugan and Sreeleka (2020); Tsedenia (2020); Rao (2022); Oak (2023).

From the study it reveals that work-life balance is positively and significantly related to employees performance of female staff at achievers university which aligns with the studies of Sharma *et al* (2019); Anukwuocha and Okafor (2020); Nwagbara (2020); Melayansari and Bhinekawati (2020); Aynalem, (2020); Pulhin (2020); Siwale (2020); Basak (2021); Gambo *et al* (2022); Okeke *et al* (2022); Khan *et al* (2023) during the study under review.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360)

5.1 Conclusion

This study evaluates the relationship between work-life balance and employee performance of female staff at Achievers University Owo, Ondo state. Three components of work-life balance were examined which are long-working hours, leisure or relaxation time and stress level in determining the relationship with employees' performance. The results show that long-working hours are positively and significantly related to employees' performance, leisure or relaxation time is negatively and significantly related to employees' performance while stress level shows a positive but insignificant relationship with employees' performance. In summary, it indicates that work-life balance has a positive and significant relationship with employees' performance during the period of the study.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the result above, the following recommendations are highlighted below:

- i. The institution should provide various work-life balance practices such as more leisure or relaxation time working environment as this will improve employees' performance.
- ii. The institution should sketch out a schedule for reasonable long-working hours so that female staff will not be overwhelmed with job or responsibilities
- iii. The institution management should work out good vacation periods that will assist females in terms of maternity, and childcare periods amongst others.
- iv. Employees should create strategies for balancing their work life to avoid stress and health challenges.

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Received: 8 February 2025

Revised: 21 March 2025

Accepted: 31 March 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15323360)

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